

The benefits and challenges of understanding funding flows in the Global South

[Tracking Research Funding Flows Project](#), April 9th 2026

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Key insights

1. In periods of funding scarcity, **new evidence and data to support global coordination can enhance impact and reduce duplication** through more targeted use of funding instruments and through leveraging existing regional and national research strengths across the Global South.
2. **Research funding flows data is a key public good to support development objectives and a more inclusive and equitable global research landscape.** Despite significant recent improvements in the coverage and quality of data and metadata, **there are major gaps that** affect comparability at a global scale and limit the potential to do research on research, promote transparency, shape equitable partnerships and support strategic funding decisions.
3. Analysis of flows should concern not only bibliometric information such as abstracts, fields and recipients but **should also address research agendas setting, policy instruments, capacity building and interactions with regional and local stakeholders.** Data and tools must be accompanied by new analytical expertise, networks and a consideration of the various political economies that underpin research funding.
4. Understanding **funding flows also requires mixed-method research that explain the conditions and contexts of application of the funding**, e.g. in terms of equal partnerships. New analyses are only beginning to produce insights to directly inform the choice of instruments, geographies, partnerships for funders to effectively direct resources to priorities.
5. Data improvements and new tools for curating or analysing funding flows **need to be associated with stronger global and regional networks** that help analyse and move data-driven insights into action.

1. The rationales for tracking, mapping and analysing funding flows

How S&T funding is allocated and managed strongly shapes its various contributions to society, e.g. in terms of progress towards various sustainable development goals (SDGs). As funders target the societal challenges they aim to address and/or the capabilities they seek to build, it is essential to better link funding strategies and research portfolios to expected impacts.

Because funding landscapes are populated by multiple funders, a system level-view is needed to identify gaps, overlaps and complementarities, so that coordination can improve impact and reduce inefficiencies.¹ This is particularly important in a context of budget reductions and geopolitical tensions.

A more systemic approach is especially relevant in those countries in the Global South with low research capacities and low domestic R&D investments (often well below 1% of GDP). Aligning research investment and outputs with national and local needs is critical, particularly where international funding strongly influences research priorities.

Data on publicly funded research, like the research itself, is a public good. In accordance to the UNESCO recommendation of Open Science, with its explicit framework on values such as collective benefits, inclusion and diversity, understanding R&D funding flows is not only valuable in terms of transparency and accountability of R&D expenditure, but crucially it is also a means of making the research system more responsive and better aligned to societal needs and challenges, and more equitable. This is particularly important in low and middle-income country contexts, where there are often competing pressures for devoting public funds to support science, as well limited resources for accessing data and tools that help manage research.

2. The benefits of new analytical and mapping methods

Conventional R&D statistics are seldom sufficiently fine-grained to capture specific fields or topics of investment. However, with the digitalisation of administrative records of projects and analytical advances in semantic algorithms, it has become possible to produce more detailed descriptions of the contents, recipients and outputs of funding.

Analysing funding flows with these new ‘mapping’ methods allows an understanding of how research is distributed across territories, themes or topics, and how funding instruments shape research landscape. We call these methods ‘mapping’ because they assign publications or grants to categories in ways that allow to produce a visualisation (a ‘map’) of the topics addressed by organisations, funders or territories. Such detailed analyses can help in improving accountability, developing strategies and fostering redistribution of resources according to policy goals.

At the thematic level, funding information can illuminate the existence of gaps and duplications and help balance the support between diverse topics in funding portfolios. This is important in order to **strategically align and design funding instruments to address societal needs**. In health research there is a long history of contrasting funding and publications with disease burden to identify understudied

¹ Chalmers et al. (2014). [How to increase value and reduce waste when research priorities are set](#). The Lancet, 383(9912), 156-165.

diseases. This has been widely applied, for example, by the US NIH to compare their funding priorities against in health needs according to disease burden estimates (both national and global).²

In the absence of robust funding data, past analyses have often sought to **contrast disease burden with the number of publications** as a proxy for the level of research effort, as shown in Figure 1. They show that upper middle-income countries (and India in particular) are making a disproportionately high effort in cancer in relation to its disease burden in their territories, whereas the opposite is true for cardiovascular diseases. Similar studies have been conducted in fields such as agriculture and nutrition, using publication data. Yet comprehensive studies focused on the Global South remain scarce. This type of comparisons of research efforts against societal needs could be conducted in terms of research expenditure if more comprehensive funding data was publicly available.

Figure 1. Comparison between relative disease burden (estimated in Disability Adjusted Life Years) and relative research efforts (estimated in publications) for cancer and cardiovascular diseases in various country income level. Source: Kumar et al. (2024).³

Another approach is to **highlight research approaches that are relatively over- or under-utilized** for a given issue. For example a recent study of global funding for cancer research was able to show not only the type of cancer studied, but also the type of research approach (pre-clinical, phase 1-4, public health, cross-disciplinary), as shown in Figure 2.⁴ Using new AI tools for semantic analyses, it is possible to make more fine-grained analyses, both in terms of research topics and in terms of type of grants. Such approaches have been used both in health (e.g. in obesity) and agriculture and food (e.g. in rice research)⁵, showing that research tends to concentrate in some topics that are not necessarily those which have the most impact in terms of improving quality of life or livelihoods.

² Gross, C. P. et al. (1999). [The relation between funding by the National Institutes of Health and the burden of disease](#). *New England Journal of Medicine*, 340(24), 1881-1887. Røttingen, J.-A. et al. (2013). [Mapping of available health research and development data](#). *The Lancet*, 382(9900).

³ Kumar et al. (2024). [Priorities of health research in India: Evidence of misalignment between research outputs and disease burden](#). *Scientometrics*, 129(4), 2433-2450. See also Yegros-Yegros, et al. (2020). [Exploring why global health needs are unmet by research efforts](#). *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 18(1), 47.

⁴ McIntosh et al. (2023). [Global funding for cancer research between 2016 and 2020: A content analysis of public and philanthropic investments](#). *The Lancet Oncology*, 24(6), 636-645.

⁵ Cassi et al. (2017). [Improving fitness: Mapping research priorities against societal needs on obesity](#). *Journal of Informetrics*, 11(4), 1095-1113. Ciarli, T., & Ràfols, I. (2019). [The relation between research priorities and societal demands: The case of rice](#). *Research Policy*, 48(4), 949-967.

At the geographical level, analyses of funding can show North / South inequalities across (and within) regions and countries and the concentration of research in cities. These analyses are vital for thinking about how to address issues of **territorial inclusion in research and to consider potential gaps or strengths in terms of research capabilities**. This approach, for example, has helped contrast climate change research in Africa with global research patterns.⁶

Figure 2. Global funding for cancer per year by type of science (A) and proportion of funding per year by type of science (B). Source: McIntosh et al. (2023).

Funding data can also be useful to **understand the effects of specific funding instruments**, such as thematic or collaborative targeted programmes. For example, one can compare the thematic focus of the funding instruments of the EU Framework Programme. As illustrated in Figure 3, the grants of the European Research Council (ERC) (on the left), appear in the periphery of the map – indicating a narrow disciplinary focus associated with fundamental science such as astrophysics, literature or molecular biology. However, the grants funded by European Innovation Council (EIC) plus the Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) Instrument, appear in topics that are more central (more interdisciplinary) such as food science and various fields related to engineering, such as digitalisation, energy and sustainability, which are more associated with innovation. In short, having a picture of the full funding landscape allows to locate funding instruments, their specificity, and their potential overlaps and complementarities.

More broadly, the **improvement of the transparency of research funding** through these types of data can help in fostering trust in science in a moment in which according to the International Science Council (ISC) ‘hidden funding links can be used to distort scientific findings, mislead the public, and suppress evidence.’⁷

In spite of the preceding examples relating to funding instruments, geographic patterns, research approaches and potential mismatches in terms of societal benefits, actual detailed funding data has

⁶ Overland et al. (2022). [Funding flows for climate change research on Africa: Where do they come from and where do they go?](#) *Climate and Development*, 14(8), 705–724.

⁷ <https://council.science/statements/isc-position-on-research-funding-transparency/>

so far been very underused for understanding the dynamics of research in the Global South and enhancing the transparency of research expenditures.

Figure 3. The relative position of two funding instruments of the European Commission on a global map of science based on grants: the European Research Council (ERC) (left) funds fundamental science in the periphery of the map; whereas the European Innovation Council plus the SME Instrument plus (right) fund more interdisciplinary and innovation-oriented research in the centre. Source: Plazas Vidal et al. (2026).⁸

3. Information sources for mapping funding flows

Given the diversity of organisations that fund and support science, from research ministries to development banks to NGOs, funding schemes take a wide variety of forms. As a consequence, different data sources are needed to capture them, raising challenges of data integration and comparability.

Statistics of R&D expenditure based on surveys conducted by National Statistical Offices and collected by international organisations such as the UNESCO, OECD and RICYT provide aggregate estimates of funding. They distinguish between fields and research stage (basic, applied, development), and between public, private, non-profit and foreign sources, as shown in Figure 4 for Africa, Asia and Pacific for 2020. Very different patterns are observed across regions. For example, African countries such as Kenya, Uganda, Mali, Mozambique and Tanzania have a foreign R&D investment above 40%, whereas East Asian countries have more than 75% of R&D from private firms. In many middle-income countries, government R&D is the largest R&D contributor. While these figures are useful as baselines, the accuracy, robustness and comparability of the estimates provided by countries with low R&D expenditure is often contested. It has long been argued that richer and more detailed approaches are needed.⁹

Complementary efforts across global health areas are conducted by actors interested in specific research sectors such as health or energy. For example, the [G-Finder survey](#) collects a survey on R&D

⁸ Plazas Vidal, et al. (2026). [A global map of science according to a topic model of EU grants](https://www.leidenmadtrics.nl/articles/the-global-map-of-science-according-to-eu-funding). QSS. See <https://www.leidenmadtrics.nl/articles/the-global-map-of-science-according-to-eu-funding>

⁹ Lepori, B. (2006). [Methodologies for the analysis of research funding and expenditure: From input to positioning indicators](#). Research Evaluation, 15(2), 133–143.

funding for new products and technologies that mainly affect the world's most disadvantaged populations, including in this case funding for technology and innovation.

Figure 4. Global Investments in R&D in the Africa, Asia and Pacific, in terms of the relative importance of the source of investment business (purple), government (orange), higher education (red), private non-profit (dark green) and foreign (khaki green). Source: Unesco (2020). [Fact Sheet No. 59 June 2020 FS/2020/SCI/59](#).

Funding acknowledgements in publications, available in bibliographic databases, may provide another point of entry. Acknowledgements allow a very fine-grained description of the outputs (publications) supported by research funding agencies, in terms of organisations, topics and location. Thus, acknowledgements can be useful for analysing the funding of the main national agencies. However, they have three limitations: they do not provide expenditure data, multiple funders are often acknowledged and reporting of funding acknowledgements is poor for many funders, especially in the Global South.

For international funding flows the major hurdle is that it is generally unclear which particular authors or organisations received the funding indicated, given that in most cases funding acknowledgements of collaborative publications cannot be linked to individual authors (nor their organisations). This means, for example, that in a collaboration between Kenyan and Chinese authors acknowledging a Chinese funder, we cannot know who received most of the funding. This ambiguity renders funding acknowledgements of limited value to track international funding flows until the assignment of funding meta-data is improved.

Administrative information of funded projects is reported since the 2010s by some major funders in dedicated websites such as the [EU CORDIS](#), the [UKRI's Gateway to Research](#) and the [NIH Reporter](#). [CrossRef indexes grants](#) that are registered by funders. In the wake of this information, various databases have collected grant data, following the pioneering efforts of [Digital Science's Dimensions](#). Several S&T Indicator initiatives are also using grant data. For example, the [Global Observatory of](#)

[Health Research and Development](#) established by the WHO, collects grant data from [13 funders](#).¹⁰ The OECD also established an [Expert Group on the Management and Analysis of R&D and Innovation Administrative Data \(MARIAD\)](#), starting with an analysis of COVID. In the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#), open grant data was chosen as one of the priorities for development. In this context, the open database [OpenAlex is making a grant indexation effort](#) with the support of Wellcome Trust.

These grant databases represent a sea change in the analysis of R&D funding and provide new analytical opportunities, as shown by a variety of recent studies, as listed above. However, grant data availability is limited to the leading scientific countries. Current databases cover main funders in North America, North/West Europe and East Asia, but even the most comprehensive database (*Dimensions*) does not cover data from most of the Global South, and data from the major funders in Brazil, South Africa and Chile is partial.

Moreover, a blind spot for this type of data is that it often only reports on resources going to the researchers coordinating projects (often in the Global North) without capturing flows to collaborators (sometimes known as *pass-through funding*), with various degrees of informality. These smaller and informal flows can constitute an important percentage of the total flows and have major effects in research agendas, but they are very difficult to capture.

With all these caveats, using *Dimensions* we have estimated cross-regional funding flows to be 1.6bn US\$ per year since 2015, with a slight decline from 1.8bn US\$ in 2010-15 as shown in Figure 5. The decline is more steep for the funding to the Global South, decreasing from 850 M US\$ (48% of total) per year in 2010-14, to 540 M US\$ (35% of total) in 2020-14. Similarly, the funding for world organisations such as the WHO decreased from 291 M US\$ (16% of total) per year in 2010-14, to 140 M US\$ (9% of total) in 2020-14. Most of the funding flows originate in North America (72%, since 2015 about 1.15bn US\$ per year), and almost all the rest, in Europe (25%, 408 M US\$ per year) – but this is likely to reflect a bias in the database coverage.

¹⁰ Ralaidovy et al. (2020). [Resource allocation for biomedical research: analysis of investments by major funders](#). *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 18(1), 20.

Figure 5. Funding flows across world regions according to grant data available in Dimensions in 2000-24. The picture is partial since ODA funding and funders in the Global South are missing. Legends: NA: North America. EUR: Europe. EA: East Asia. OCE: Oceania. WLD: World organisations. LAC: Latin America and Caribe. SSA: Sub-Saharan Africa. NWA: North Africa and West Asia. CSA: Central and South Asa. SEA: South East Asia.

A major gap is that current grant databases do not include funding for research provided by **Official Development Assistance (ODA)** agencies such as SIDA or NORAD. There are alternative data sources for this purpose: the OECD [Creditor Reporting System \(CRS\)](#) for ODA (which includes 10 categories related to research), the [Financial Tracking Service](#) for Humanitarian Aid Contribution, the [Total Official Support for Sustainable Development](#) and the [International Aid Transparency Initiative \(IATI\)](#) (including some research categories). While each of these may provide valuable information, it is unclear to which extent these sources provide a comprehensive or partial coverage, and to which extent 'research' is defined the same way as in research funders databases.

This gap is important since research funding from ODA is estimated to be larger than from research funders: taking into account only funding by OECD countries, it was estimated that ODA-related research in the order of 1.7 bn US\$ about 1% of total ODA in 2022 (down from 2.7 bn US\$ in 2018), in comparison to our Dimensions estimate of about 0.54 bn US\$ from research funders.¹¹ Therefore, ODA related research needs to be taken into account.

One can envisage bringing these different information sources together in order to produce a comprehensive picture. For example, the project 'STI Funding in Africa' led by Johan Mouton in Stellenbosch University has integrated different information sources and visualised it in a dashboard.¹² The resulting amounts of cross-regional funding flows to Africa are well-above the estimates obtained solely with the science-focused funders captured with a single database in Figure 5.

4. Understanding the contexts and conditions of funding flows

While the quantitative data on funding is important, funding flows need to be qualified by the policy and social contexts in which funding is awarded. In other words, we need to understand not just the amount of money spent on R&D but also the regional and national policy and research environments, for what purposes, under which conditions, and according to which (and whose) rules research funding is awarded and implemented. All these aspects are salient given that power imbalances in these spaces and configurations often result in unequal collaborations in the global research.

The analysis of **design and implementation of funding instruments is a major gap** in current analyses. Different funding instruments (i.e. different programmes and calls for proposals) have particular missions and goals, specific priorities and research modes, procedures and rules for submission as well as for execution. These variety of conditions for receiving and executing grants result in disparate outcomes and effects. It is thus crucial to understand **the conditions of funding instruments** so to

¹¹ Estimation provided in <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2025/10/13/what-we-can-learn-from-tracking-research-funding-flows-from-north-to-south/>

¹² <https://db.crest.sun.ac.za/idrc-dashboard/>. See description of results in Mouton (2025) The state of STI in Africa: Funding flows and the role of Science Granting Councils. Stellenbosch University.

assess their relevance and whether they are ‘fit for purpose’.¹³ However, current grant databases provide, in the best of cases, only the label of the funding schemes.

There is a pressing need to study funding instruments in particular national contexts, according to characteristics such as their narrow or broad scope, as well as their academic, policy, industrial or social emphases. In particular, the outcomes of grants supported by **goal-oriented or targeted funding** instruments depend heavily on the conditions and design of the funding: the requirements for diversity and type of stakeholders, the modes of stakeholders’ participation in problem definition and research, the grant size and duration, the degree of transdisciplinarity in the consortium. The variety of factors affecting targeted funding is far less understood than collaboration dynamics and needs to be more studied.¹⁴

Two other issues deserve further attention. The first, is the **degree of autonomy** awarded by the funding instrument to participants from the Global South. Funding instruments that support international flows and collaborations are often coordinated by Northern partners. This architecture has been critically assessed as resulting in **unequal partnerships** (**‘subordinate integration’**), in which the research framing is given by Northern funders or coordinators.¹⁵ There is growing awareness that Southern organisations ought to be in leading positions for research to respond and eventually contribute to local needs and aspirations.¹⁶ This is reflected in the recent [Africa Charter for Transformative Research Collaborations](#) and the [Cape Town Statement](#), both firmly rooted in the 2021 UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science.

Second, since the research environments of regions and countries are extremely different, funding needs to be situated according to existing national institutions and capabilities. There should be explicit discussions on whether funding instruments should focus primarily on supporting solutions to specific topics or whether they should also aim to **build capacity** that can be applied to many areas of expertise. This of course strongly depends on existing capabilities. It has long been argued that a capacity-building approach to research is better suited for longer term goals: research will rarely provide silver-bullet solutions but it often develops diverse types of expertise that help solve problems.¹⁷ Without research capacity, problem-oriented funding instruments are unlikely to work.

In this respect, it is also worth increasing a focus on **regional research dynamics**. While some countries may have low R&D investment and limited research capacity, neighbour countries in the same region of the Global South may have both critical mass and research strengths, may share similar STI systems, similar pressing needs (e.g. in health or the environment) and similar linguistic or cultural profiles. This could, in many instances, imply that a regional lens to North-South or South-South collaboration would

¹³ Ramos-Vielba et al. (2024) [How can societally-targeted research funding shape researcher networks and practices?](#), *Research Evaluation*, rvae019. Gläser & Laudel (2016). [Governing science: How science policy shapes research content](#). *European Journal of sociology*, 57(1), 117-168.

¹⁴ Reale, E., Gulbrandsen, M., & Scherngell, T. (2023). [RD programs as instruments for governmental RD funding policy](#). In B. Lepori, B. Jongbloed, & D. Hicks (Eds), *Handbook of Public Funding of Research* (pp. 107–122). Edward Elgar Publishing. Schneider et al. (2019). [Research funding programmes aiming for societal transformations: Ten key stages](#). *Science and Public Policy*, 46(3), 463-478.

¹⁵ Feld, A., & Kreimer, P. (2019). Scientific co-operation and centre-periphery relations: attitudes and interests of European and Latin American scientists. *Tapuya: Latin American Science, Technology and Society*, 2(1), 149-175.

¹⁶ See for example Dodson (2017) [Building partnerships of equals](#). UKCS, and https://globalresearch.scnat.ch/en/grp-guide/in_depth/research_partnerships

¹⁷ <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2025/10/13/what-we-can-learn-from-tracking-research-funding-flows-from-north-to-south/>

have a greater impact. In addition, many countries in the Global South show an extremely high level of concentration in research elites (often reinforced by the prestige conferred by collaborations with partners or funders in the North) in a few institutions (often in large cities). There can be a disconnect with ‘peripheral’ realities (often in rural areas) rooted in local innovation networks and the engagement of non-traditional actors in the research enterprise. Analysing funding flows and capability building from geographical and regional perspectives may help enhance regional collaboration and promote new modalities for supporting research that reflect local networks and priorities.

In summary, it is not enough having data on the funding flows, we also need a description of policy instruments and processes that explain how they operate: in which institutional environments, for what purposes and under which conditions are being used, with which localised social impacts. For this wider understanding, we will need case studies of specific regional contexts with qualitative and mixed-method analyses, as well as better tools and networks to engage policymakers and researchers from the Global South.

5. Looking ahead: understanding research funding flows in a rapidly changing global landscape

We are in a new reality in which science policy rationales shift towards policy-goals, mission-orientation and global challenges, yet geopolitical transformations may be leading to a reduction of research resources, international cooperation, and development assistance overall. We need to find ways to mitigate these trends which could otherwise be very detrimental to development in the Global South and shared global challenges. In this context, in order to better inform how research can support development objectives, it is fundamental for funders to understand both national and international funding flows in the various regions of the Global South.

To do so, we need on the one hand more comprehensive funding data, including funders in the Global South, national research agencies and philanthropic organisations in the Global North, as well as R&D funding from ODA envelopes. Also, this data must be made available in ways that are accessible to different technical levels of various analytical capacities (from [raw data to dashboards](#)) and key users from the Global South must play a central role in informing the development of these tools and metadata, and have the capacity to use them effectively.

On the other hand, situated analyses on how the diverse funding instruments and partnerships are developed and yield some outcomes (and not others) are also needed. Research on research (or metascience, with all its long historical precursors and distinct disciplinary paths) should and can help in understanding how specific funding flows in the Global South have (or have not) contributed to social outcomes. This knowledge can then be mobilised in a period of funding scarcity to coordinate efforts towards the most pressing needs.

With this knowledge, better funding instruments and implementation can result in major improvement in terms of impact, inclusivity, diversity in the global research funding landscape.